

Impact of Persistent Trade Deficit on Economic Growth: Evidence from Four Africa Regions

Author's Details:

¹**Hu Xuhua (PhD Professor)** xhahux@ujs.edu.cn Executive Dean, Director of Division of Open Economy & Industry Development - Jiangsu University, School of Finance and Economics, Zhenjiang, China

²**Ernest Kay Bakpa** - ernestkay1481@gmail.com <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5975-1736> Overseas Education College School of Finance and Economics, Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang, China

Competing Financial Interests;

the authors declare no competing financial interests whatsoever about this paper.

Acknowledgment

the authors wish to thank the National Science Foundation of China (NSFC 71203079) for the financial support

&

The Ministry of Education Humanities and Social Science Fund Project: 16YJC790031

Abstract

This paper examines the impact of chronic and persistent trade deficit on economic growth in Africa for the period between 1980 and 2017. In this study, the data from the world bank database covered four regions of Africa namely; Central Africa, East Africa, North Africa, and West Africa. Generalized Method of Moment (GMM) estimator, Random Effect Model (RE) and Generalized Linear Model (GLM) was adopted in analyzing the data. Results from the study show that the trade deficit is caused by high inflation rate and low export production. Also, the result indicates that the unstable exchange rate is one of the main causes of the trade deficit in these regions. The paper, therefore, recommends that inflation rate should be reduced to a level that can induce trade balance and reduce the high pricing of goods. Further, there should be proper allocation of resources to the export production sectors.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Trade deficit, Inflation, Exchange rate;

Introduction

Economic growth of a nation depends on efficiency and productivity and it is most advantageous if the nation exports the goods and records positive trade balance according to Ricardo's competitive advantage theory. Africa countries terms of trade are always unfavorable (trade deficit). Trade Deficit represents an outflow of domestic currency to the foreign market. Thus, the Total value of import minus Total value of export which is also called a negative balance of trade (Lemi, 2017; Were, 2015). A trade deficit occurs when a country imports more goods more and export less. With the trade deficit, a nation is said to be undergoing economics undergrowth in the sense that much of the nation's income is used for paying debts. Most countries in Africa are agricultural-driven economy that depends heavily on both commercial and subsistence agriculture, which provides great significant employment to the people. (Diao & McMillan, 2018).

Most African countries are an agricultural-driven economy that has a large fertile land for the cultivation of primary product for export and have a large deposit of natural resources such as Oil and Gas, Golds, Dimond, Copper, Bauxite, Coal, Uranium, Platinum, Aluminum, Iron and Steel just to name but a few. Africa also among other capitals goods produce cash crops such as Cocoa, coffee, cotton, Tea, Tobacco, Oil-palm, and Rubber also just to name but a few. Despite all this large deposit, Africa is persistently recoding trade deficit "time to time out". The table below shows on average, trade balance of some developed Africa countries base on the real GDP growth.

Table 1. 1 Some Selected Africa Countries from Four Regions on Africa

COUNTRIES	2006-2011 (Years)	2012-2016 (Years)
Cabo Verde	-4.56306	-5.25780
Congo, Dem. Rep.	-5.2343	-8.78053
Egypt	-10.2266	-11.6795
Equatorial Guinea	-10.1716	-17.5991
Gabon	-11.0395	-11.4194
Ghana	-29.4647	-20.2100
Kenya	-3.93402	-10.5708
Mauritius	-7.46244	-8.62319
Morocco	-27.3317	-29.7118
Namibia	-28.0345	-19.0261
Nigeria	-11.8331	-8.80438
Sao Tome and Principe	-7.35729	-4.72025
Seychelles	-12.6932	-20.3785
Tunisia	-16.5323	-20.2624
Libya	-9.50865	-6.94753
Algeria	-21.1777	-5.09962
Togo	-16.5323	-20.2624

From the table, it shows that the real GDP growth in these Four regions of Africa, Central Africa, North Africa, East Africa, and West Africa are negative for the past ten years from trade on average

According to (Prebisch, Abdoh, & Decolonization, 2017) most Africa countries are exploited and do not benefit from trade and adding to the real GDP growth. This is mostly a result of too much importation from the developed countries and less export back to the developed countries. This in both the long-run and the short-run kills the infant industries. Therefore, developing countries should keep out imported goods until the infant industries become competitive (Lin & Chang, 2009). According to (Balassa, 2016) and (Connolly & Hanson, 2016), poor or developing countries should adopt import substitution policy and the Less Developing Countries (LDCs) should export primary products in order to correct the trade deficit in the economy. base on the above studies, African countries should adopt export production policies and import substitution.

The aim of the study

There has been a lot of research on trade and economic growth by (McCombie & Thirlwall, 2016), (Osakwe, Santos-Paulino, & Dogan, 2018) and (Zahonogo, 2016), inflation and economic growth by (Ndou & Gumata, 2017), cause of trade deficit by (Steinberg, 2018), exchange rate inflation and growth by (Senadza & Diaba, 2017), (Ouyang, Rajan, & Li, 2016) and (Tamgac, 2013), industries and trade by (Hartwell, 2017), the growth theory by (Meinen & Raff, 2018). But there has not been much study on the persistent trade deficit on Africa considering inflation, exchange rate, industries all put together as the cause of trade deficit. Hence our study seeks to examine the main impact of trade deficit on Economic Growth considering inflation, exchange rate and industries and again to identify the main impact of these three variables on trade. Does the study seek to ask the question (a) what is the main cause of the persistent trade deficit on the economic growth in Africa? (b) what main factors can be associated with this persistent trade deficit in Africa? (c) what is the way out of the persistent trade deficit in Africa? The study also works around the hypothesis that trade deficit is a result of low industrial production (b), the persistent trade deficit is as a result of the higher rate of inflation, (c) persistent trade deficit is totally negative to economic growth.

Review of Some Selected Literatures

The general aim of this study is to examine the main impact of the Trade Deficit on Economic Growth on the four regions in Africa. The imperative point of our study is to know the impact of the trade deficit on Economic

Growth and whether the trade deficit is imperative or detrimental to economic growth. Some researchers argue that trade deficit means the economy is living beyond its means and gathering or amounting too much debt in the economy. Sometimes trade deficit can be positive for economic growth or negative growth, which all depends on the underlining factors that make up the deficit component or the long-run effect of the deficit. According to theories underlining trade deficit, it states that deficit occurs when a nation or a country spends more foreign currency or money yearly on import more than it gets from exports.

When a nation persistently records trade deficit, the negative effect on economic growth and stability are a mostly higher rate of unemployment in the domestic country (Rjoub, Aga, Oppong, Sunju, & Fofack, 2017). This is to say that if the import rates are more than the export rate, local or domestic jobs may be the loss to workers abroad. In some cases, the unemployment rate can sometimes be high in the presence of trade surpluses. Other theories also suggest that if the demand for a nation's export is high, the local currency of that nation becomes high, but if the import is more than export then the exchange rate will also decline making import more expensive (Menyah, Nazlioglu, & Wolde-Rufael, 2014). So, in return, the local currency of that country becomes devalued in the world market. According to the floating exchange rate system, negative trade balance (trade deficit) should be theoretically corrected with the adjustment in the exchange markets. It can also mean that the persistent trade deficit of a nation means that the local currency of that nation is highly desired in the global market.

According to theories, the persistent trade deficit should be offset by the surplus in the nation's capital account and the financial account. With the persistent trade deficit, the nation is likely to have a less return from Foreign Direct Investment thereby increasing government foreign debt (Ojo & Oluwatayo, 2016). With most of the African economies, this could lead to the detriment of economic growth seeing that more of the nation's asset is owned and controlled by foreigners who influence the uses of the nation's natural resources. But in all, according to Milton Friedman, the negative trade balance is not harmful in the long-run effect because it leads to technology spillover and the local currency returning into the domestic market through foreign investment. But in all a huge trade deficit simply means that there is a high consumer preference and in the long-run does not really matters to the economy because the citizens are getting what they want and needs.

Trade and the Industries

Industries are the bed-rock of trade in the sense that low productivity will result in lower export (Morris & Fessehaie, 2014). According to Ricardo's competitive advantage theory, economic development depends on efficiency and productivity and with less productivity in an economy, the nation is said to be underdeveloped. So, if the industry sector of the economy contributes or is inefficient in production and less productive, that economy is likely to record trade deficit. Therefore, before a nation can meet the stranded of trade, that nation needs to efficient in production through proper allocation of resources (Geda & Seid, 2015; Osakwe et al., 2018). In the case of Africa, the primary product industries need to be properly controlled in order to produce much for export (Mbate, 2016; Njikam, 2017). According to studies, there is a positive relation between export production and economic growth.

Therefore, it is expected that high export production will lead to the correction of the trade deficit and the creation of more jobs and a better standard of living. A decline in the export product sector will result in a trade deficit. Modern trade theory demonstrates that the gains from trade depend critically on a reallocation of production from small to large firms (Mold & Mukwaya, 2016; Seck, 2016). What this means is that the decline in the exporting industries might be as a result of misallocation of resources or the industries are not big enough to meet the demand on the external market. If industries that are to produce for export are declining and inefficient, they may need an important or bigger investment to make them efficient. In that way, protection for these declining exporting industries would act as a motivation for these firms to invest and reinvent themselves. Therefore, protectionism could also be justification for protecting these inefficient firms for them to produce for the external market.

Trade and Inflation

Trade between countries and its policies are most time if not always difficult enough to comprehend when price

levels remain the same for a long period of time. But the addition of chronic or rapid rate of inflation, it becomes more difficult in understanding some of the economic principles (Franses & Janssens, 2018; Oikawa & Ueda, 2018). This is because general price inflation leads to changes in the real income level and the level of distribution within countries and across national boundaries. According to the basic definition of Inflation, it is a continual increase in the general price level in the economy, which is measured either at the retail or wholesale level.

Annually, the rate of change in the price level is commonly expressed in index numbers as the inflation rate in an economy (Ndou & Gumata, 2017).

Trade deficit naturally occurs when a country does not produce much-needed goods to meet the growing population's demand. On the other hand, a deficit indicates that the consumer is well-off enough to purchase more commodities than the country produces. If this happens, and since the consumers are wealthy enough to pay for the commodities, inflation sets in. This then leads to import from other nations to meet the demand of the population by increasing the export level of the other country. A trade deficit is not necessarily unfavorable because it often corrects itself over time (Steinberg, 2018).

An increase in imported goods and services from other countries decreases the price level of consumer goods and services in the nation as foreign competition increases (Khan & Ssnhadji, 2001). The lower prices help to reduce the threat of inflation in the local economy. If a country's inflation rate rises faster than its main competitors, then it makes that country's exports less competitive and imports more competitive. This will then lead to deterioration in the country's trade balance (Nguyen, Dridi, Unsal, & Williams, 2017; Yanamandra, 2015). However, inflation may also lead to a depreciation in the currency to offset this decline in competitiveness. Inflation also tends to change currency exchange rates and the international balance of payments accounts (Buffie, Airaud, & Zanna, 2018; de Mendonça & Tiberto, 2017; Wu & Wu, 2018).

For example, if there is a rapid and constant increase in inflation rate in an economy and another trading nation, it will lead to changes in the relative prices but will hold cost ratio constant over time (Gokal & Hanif, 2004). And since exchange rates are price relatives, it will lead to exchange rates, which would change in response to rapid inflation rate. (Bowdler & Malik, 2017). Thus, there will be no price-induced changes in imports, and exports, or balance of payments would occur. This example, one way or the other might not hold because it will be very difficult holding rapid and equal inflation rate unless the rapid and equal inflation rates are accompanied by an unequal rate of changes in the real income. This could emerge because of the differential rate of the growth in the real GDP across economies. Moreover, the unequal changes in the real income could also induce changes in goods and services and Exchange rate through changes or shift in demand which will not be inflation or serious inflation issue (Ghosh, 2014; Ouyang et al., 2016).

More so, if importing and exporting economies display a very substantial different domestic inflation rate, which affects goods and services both trading and non-trading, exchange rate of the exporting economy's currency which is fixed as against the other nation which is not fixed so the relative price across both economies will change at a rate that will be equal to the difference between the two economies. Again, if an economy holds a fixed exchange rate (Klein & Shambaugh, 2006), the export of the rapid inflating rate will be control thereby making import to that rapid inflating nation more expensive leading to trade deficit in the importing economy. (Ngo, 2017; Tamgac, 2013).

Trade and Exchange Rate

Anticipation of inflation has real effects on trade and economic growth of a nation through its role as a tax on money and on all monetary transactions in an economy (Friedman, 2017; Kassim, 2016; Krugman, 2017). An upward or increase in the rate of monetary growth generally reduces the value of gross domestic output and alters the composition of all domestic production. This monetary growth results in the changes in the pattern of international comparative advantage and trade flows (Gilpin, 2016; Hale & Obstfeld, 2016; Levchenko & Zhang, 2016). Most exchange rate and monetary theories hold that initial depreciation of the exchange rate as a

result of increase in the rate of monetary growth is mostly accompanied by a trade surplus (Krugman, 2017; Ndou & Gumata, 2017) and capital outflow whereas the subsequent depreciation is mostly accompanied by a trade deficit in the economy. Movements in the exchange rate mostly influence imports and exports, and nominal depreciation or appreciation of the exchange rate is presumed to change the real exchange rate and, thus, have a direct effect on a country's trade balance.

If the currency of a nation become overvalued, imports become cheaper resulting in a higher volume of import and making export becomes uncompetitive and then leads to falling in the export volume. According to trade theory on the exchange rate, a real depreciation (Chen & Juvenal, 2016) or the devaluation of the local currency would cause imports to be more expensive and exports become cheaper and eventually leads to an improvement in the trade balance (Gervais, Schembri, & Suchanek, 2016). This will discourage importation and in both long-run and short-run will make export cheaper which will also in both long-run and short-run leads to correction of trade deficit. The low price of export does not lead to trade deficit but only correct the deficit (Arize, Malindretos, Igwe, & Finance, 2017).

According to (Gervais et al., 2016), with the price of import becoming more expensive as a result of the increase in the Dollar rate being the accepted currency for the international market means that the importers will now reduce the level of importation. It is also expected that the persistent trade deficit will be control by the changes in the exchange rate. Theoretically, the exchange rate is very imperative in economic activity (Senadza & Diaba, 2017). First, changes in the exchange rate thus appreciation and depreciation have a solid impact on the direction of trade. If a nation's exchange rate experiences depreciation but holding other factors constant, that nation's goods and services become cheaper relative to those of the nation's trade partners.

Model specification

To measure the impact of the Trade Deficit on economic growth, the model follows;

$$Y = C + I + G + (X - M) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where;

Y = the real GDP of the economy, C = consumption I= Investments G= Government expenditure

This than follows that the trade deficit which is the net Export of the economy is translated to be;

$$td_{it} = x_{it} - m_{it} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

“td” = trade deficit, “x” = export, “m” = import, “i and t” are indices for individual and time

From the model, changes in any of the variables can lead to a trade deficit.

The Main Impact of Trade Deficit on Economic Growth

$$Y_{it} = \gamma_0 + \beta_1 y_{i(t-1)} + \beta_2 td_{it} + \beta_3 Ifn_{it} + \beta_4 Ind_{it} + \beta_5 Fe_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

The main aim of the study is to determine the main impact of trade deficit on the real GDP. It holds that to be able to determine the impact, some control variables must be added to the main variable to show the impact. The inclusion of Inflation, Foreign Exchange rate and Total exporting industry being the control variable is to point out the main impact on the real GDP the control variables were also transformed to have a unit base in other to get the correct impact of the trade deficit. It then follows;

Where;

Y_{it} = the real GDP $y_{i(t-1)}$ = the lag value of the GDP, td_{it} = the trade deficit at a time period “t” Ifn_{it} = Inflation rate in individual country at a time period “t” Ind_{it} = Total production industries in individual country

at a time period “t” taking into consideration depreciation Fe_{it} = Exchange rate in individual country at a time period “t” “ γ_0 ” = the constant of the model and “ $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_5, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_4$ ” = the coefficient of the variables under consideration. And “ μ_{it} ” = the error term of the model which is always a zero term

Data

Our panel data set spans the period of 1980 - 2017 from the World Bank Database covering 38 years and is made up of 15 economies whose selections were determined by the availability of data and the level of economic development. We measure trade by summing up all export of goods and services minus total summation of goods and services imported at the end of each accounting year. The variable industry was measured as the total number of export production industries in the economy as the percentage on the real GDP. After the collection of the raw data from the world bank database, we run a general test on the data to know how the data will work. Before the model can be adopted, we also run tests to see if there are any form of cross-sectional dependence in the data, if there is any independence in the data and if there is any form of Heteroskedasticity in the data which will not lead to any form of biases in the result. To also select the best model for the study we run for Hausman test of model selection and chose the best fit model for the study.

Table 1. 2 Test for independence, cross-sectional dependence Heteroskedasticity in the data.

Regions	Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier (LM) Test		Pasaran CD test for cross-sectional dependence (CD) Test		Presence of Heteroskedasticity Test
	FE	RE	Probability	Absolute Value	Prob>Chis
	Chi2	Chibar2			
Central Africa	47.784	0.000	0.024	0.366	0.000
East Africa	26.546	0.000	0.3666	0.362	0.000
North Africa	159.78	0.000	0.0000	0.373	0.000
West African	129.753	0.000	0.6506	0.577	0.000

Testing the data for independence in the data with Breusch-Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test (LM) test prove that for all four regions in Africa, it shows that there is independence in the data. Base on the null hypothesis, the LM test shows that the variance across the whole data is not zero which also means that there is a significant difference across the data or the units which also shows that there is no difference across the panel. According to studies, cross-sectional dependence in data is one of the main problems that come with macro panel data's for more than years this is mostly in the large number data's or samples and so, from table 1 it shows that there is no cross-sectional dependence in the data among all four regions in Africa.

Table 1. 2 Descriptive Statistics for the Selected Regions

Regions		Mean (%)	Std. Dev (%)	Variance (%)	Skewness (%)	Kurtosis (%)	Max (%)	Min (%)
Central Africa	GDP	3.16	5.559	3.089	1.957	5.858	2.245	-5.665
	GDP-growth	3.36	5.743	33.035	-0.117	5.879	25.007	-15.743
	Trade	-5.069	5.441	29.662	-0.216	3.464	10.083	-21.1
	inflation	245.951	2063.9	4259684	12.343	158.558	26765.86	-5.665
	industry	32.217	15.67554	245.725	1.816	8.102	104.637	0.993
	Exchange Rate	261.567	220.568	48650.41	0.277	1.144	733.038	0.024
East Africa	GDP	6.839	1.291	1.662	3.421	15.173	7.499	1.161
	GDP-growth	6.32	8.457	71.528	0.55	5.307	39.487	-24.049
	Trade	-7.098	21.918	480.398	-0.287	2.708	36.362	-61.892
	inflation	8.277	11.647	135.654	1.187	6.658	65.41	-20.809
	industry	28.277	17.898	320.358	0.41	2.189	-6.946	66.527
	Exchange Rate	20.859	24.48	599.317	1.827	5.2135	4.761	103.373
North Africa	GDP	4.611	5.731	3.282	2.559	10.65	3.411	3.338
	GDP-growth	9.452	16.041	257.327	2.09	13.987	-62.075	123.139
	Trade	-3.156	19.617	384.861	-0.359	3.9285	3.832	23.956
	inflation	9.787	11.559	133.618	0.8247	3.855	53.788	-29.172
	industry	30.706	12.683	160.876	0.093	2.737	-6.946	59.221
	Exchange Rate	9.158	20.225	409.056	3.178	12.252	0.281	110.973
West Africa	GDP	2.76	8.501	7.231	4.607	24.294	5.688	1.211
	GDP-growth	1.517	2.308	5.286	15.139	230.443	3.5	-19.685
	Trade	-14.786	56.393	3180.67	-3.466	16.232	49.76	-344.751
	inflation	15.954	15.104	228.088	2.362	15.134	113.076	-20.83
	industry	29.364	23.798	566.046	0.584	2.707	104.637	-12.304
	Exchange Rate	127.131	176.434	31130.16	1.584	4.615	733.038	0.007

Again, on the data, test for general Cross-Sectional Dependence on data for all four-region using the Pasaran "CD" test, it also shows that there is no Cross-Sectional dependence in the data except that of North Africa. The presences of cross-sectional dependence in a data will lead to bias in the result which will make the decision not accepted or valid. Also, from the table on the data, it shows that there is no heteroskedasticity in the data for all four regions.

All the variables are measured in percentage of the real GDP. From the descriptive analysis on the data for Central Africa, East Africa, North Africa and West Africa countries trade variable shows a negative mean on the real GDP of about with of -5.069, -7.098, -3.16, -14.786 and a positive standard deviation of 5.44, 21.918, 19.617 and 56.393 respectively which means that the mean value which is negative and positive stander deviation show how spreaded the data is from each other indicating how the variables or the data are not closer to each other. Again, on the data the skewness value of -0.216, -0.287, -0.359, and -3.466 of trade shows that the data for trade moves towards the left tail of the dependent variable which support the persistent trade deficit leaving negative growth rate on the real GDP.

Table 1. 3 Hausman test for model selection

Regions	variables	coefficients			
		(b)	(B)	(b-B)	S.E
		Fixed Effect	Random Effect	Difference	
Central Africa	GDP-growth	1.238	1.25	-2.196	5.256
	Trade	-2.528	-2.298	-2.287	3.357
	inflation	-1.735	-1.525	-21179.9	0
	industry	8.957	9.887	-9.276	4.926
	Exchange Rate	2.067	1.617	4440410	2074024
	Prob>Chi2	4.641			
East Africa					

	GDP-growth	1.528	1.628	-1.007	2.757
	Trade	-6.227	-5.807	-4207540	1.207
	inflation	-6.237	-6.717	4784710	6207834
	industry	1.157	5.417	-4.26E+07	4.457
	Exchange Rate	4.69	4.707	-898600	4471188
North Africa	Prob>Chi2	9.641			
	GDP-growth	-4.82	-2.388	-2.448	2.747
	Trade	1.4	-4.608	6.008	1.438
	inflation	-5.698	-7.406	-5.618	1.128
	industry	1.358	-2.588	3.938	2.208
	Exchange Rate	1.549	1.349	1.968	7.547
West Africa	Prob>Chi2	0.150			
	GDP-growth	-1.779	-7.91	-9.791	0.000
	Trade	1.058	1.558	-4.967	0.000
	inflation	5.826	9.237	-8.657	0.000
	industry	-1.978	1.318	-3.298	0.000
	Exchange Rate	3.178	1.157	3.068	3.887
	Prob>Chi2	2.403			

From the Hausman test of both random and fixed effect, the probability chi2 which is more than 0.05, show that the best model for estimating the main effect is a random effect. The condition for the selection of either effect is if the prob>chi2 is less than 0.05 or equal to 0.05, we chose the fixed effect model to run the regression but if the prob>chis2 is more than 0.05 we chose the random effect for the estimation. The Hausman test also shows that the right model to use is the random effect. This is based on the probability chi2 which is more than 0.05. for all the four regions in Africa.

Result and discussion.

Table 1. 4 Regression result from the four regions

Variables	<u>CENTRAL AFRICA</u>			<u>EAST AFRICA</u>			<u>NORTH AFRICA</u>			<u>WEST AFRICA</u>		
	(RE)	(GLM)	(GMM)	(RE)	(GLM)	(GMM)	(RE)	(GLM)	(GMM)	(RE)	GLM	GMM
$y_{i(t-1)}$	1.249** (5.637)	1.249** (5.637)	1.249*** (4.191)	1.619* (6.756)	1.619* (6.756)	1.619** (5.736)	-2.383 (2.100)	-2.383 (1.931)	-2.383 (2.251)	1.519* (7.293)	1.519* (7.293)	-4.630 (5.712)
<i>trade</i>	- 2.288** * (6.338)	- 2.288** * (6.338)	- 2.288*** (4.868)	-5.800 (3.646)	-5.800 (3.646)	- 5.800** * (2.038)	- 4.602* * (1.866)	- 4.602** * (1.636)	- 4.602** * (1.306)	-6.221 (3.839)	-6.221 (3.839)	-0.045 (0.027)
<i>inflation</i>	-51,601 (156,54 7)	-51,601 (156,54 7)	- 51,601** (41,365)	-6.710 (4.773)	-6.710 (4.773)	-6.710 (5.289)	-7.403 (3.157)	-7.403 (3.105)	-7.403 (2.220)	-6.232 (4.813)	-6.232 (4.813)	0.260* (0.155)
<i>industry</i>	9.881** * (2.188)	9.881** * (2.188)	9.881*** (1.682)	5.409 (4.250)	5.409 (4.250)	5.409** (2.324)	-2.581 (2.814)	-2.581* (1.434)	-2.581 (2.780)	1.148 (6.150)	1.148 (6.150)	0.308** (0.120)

exchange Rate	0.351*** (0.051)	0.351*** (0.051)	0.351*** (0.066)
Constant	21.18*** (0.392)	21.18*** (0.392)	21.18*** (0.570)
Observations	992	992	992
R-squared	0.692		0.085

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

To the main issuer of the study that is the main impact of the persistent trade deficit on economic growth in Africa. From the study, it shows that trade deficit impacts on Economic Growth in Africa in have a very strong negative influence. To estimate the main impact, the GMM model was used to estimate the full impact and it shows that on the real GDP growth of Africa, trade deficit contributes about -14% on the real GDP growth. And, from the GLM model, trade deficit adds to the real GDP growth a negative impact which deteriorates growth in Africa at large. From the three models of estimation, it shows that the trade deficit impacts Africa in a negative way. This negative impact is caused by the higher rate of inflation in Africa. Most Africa countries face a big problem of high rate of inflation almost every accounting year. This high rate of inflation can also be linked to the low contribution from the industrial sectors in Africa. From table 1.6, contributions from industry according to the three models of estimations shows to be at a constant level of 0.9%. meaning that the whole of Africa produces very little but import much to feed the rapid population which results in the high inflation rate. The GMM model shows the main impact of the trade deficit on Economic Growth of Africa. This shows that Africa should reduce too much import and produce more for export.

Conclusion and recommendation

This paper examines the alarming trade deficits in Africa, our study and most economic theory try to find the root causes and cures of these chronic and persistent trade deficit in Africa. It is true that these chronic and persistent trade are not "natural" phenomenon like the sciences or the plant and animal species. Moreover, the trade deficit does not ensure growth in the economy as some researchers assumed that it lends to technology spillover and growth in human capital. The empirical results strongly suggest a higher rate of inflation leads to the persistent trade deficit in an economy. This is because inflation exerts a negative effect on the price of goods and services and goes in both long-run and short-run to affect the exchange rate.

The result also suggests low productivity of the local industries is also one of the major causes of these chronic and persistent trade deficit in Africa. The study also examines the relationship between the price of goods and services and the exchange rate as another cause of the persistent trade deficit. It is established that as changes in the exchange rate affect the price of goods and services by either increasing the price of import and reducing export price which also led to higher rate of inflation and trade deficit at both the long-run and short-run.

The study concluded that the impact of these chronic and persistent trade deficit on Economic growth is totally negative in both the short-run and the Long-run. The empirical result proves that on the real GDP of these selected Africa regions, trade deficit led to negative growth in the real GDP each year thereby making most of these regions slow in development. The negative trade deficit impact on Economic growth in Africa means more of the currency is moving out of the domestic market to the international market or in other words, it means the addition of more foreign debt.

We, therefore, recommended that the best way out of this chronic and persistent trade deficit is to specialize in the production of export goods. This means that the local industries should be properly developed for export

production and more resources should be allocated to them. The large deposit of natural minerals in Africa should be will mine and export. That means the government should develop a strong policy that will control the mining of these mineral resources which will at the long-run create jobs for the citizens. Another way out of this chronic and persistent trade deficit is to control the higher rate of inflation in Africa through the imposition of higher import tax. The imposition of higher import tax will help control the exchange rate and the high import level and it will boost the local industries.

Abbreviations

(GDP) Gross Domestic Product.

Acknowledgements; We would like to thank the National Science Foundation of China (NSFC 71203079) And the Ministry of Education, Humanities and Social Science Fund Project: 16YJC790031 for the financial support

Author contributions; E.K.B designed the analysis and performed the analysis. H X. And E.K.B. analyzed results and wrote the paper.

Additional Information; Correspondence and requests for materials and data should be addressed to E.K.B

Competing Financial Interests; The authors declare no competing financial interests whatsoever

Funding:

National Science Foundation of China (NSFC 71203079) and The Ministry of Education, Humanities and Social Science Fund Project: 16YJC790031

Availability of Data and Material: The data used for this study was taken from the **World Bank databases** and **Stata** software was used in analyzing the data.

References

- i. Arize, A. C., Malindretos, J., Igwe, E. U. J. I. R. o. E., & Finance. (2017). *Do exchange rate changes improve the trade balance: An asymmetric nonlinear cointegration approach*. 49, 313-326.
- ii. Balassa, B. (2016). *Policy reform in developing countries*: Elsevier.
- iii. Bowdler, C., & Malik, A. (2017). *Openness and inflation volatility: Panel data evidence*. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 41, 57-69. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.najef.2017.03.008>
- iv. Buffie, E. F., Airaudo, M., & Zanna, F. (2018). *Inflation targeting and exchange rate management in less developed countries*. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 81, 159-184. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jimonfin.2017.09.013>
- v. Chen, N., & Juvenal, L. J. J. o. I. E. (2016). *Quality, trade, and exchange rate pass-through*. 100, 61-80.
- vi. Connolly, R., & Hanson, P. J. R. P. (2016). *Import substitution and economic sovereignty in Russia*. 1-24.
- vii. de Mendonça, H. F., & Tiberto, B. P. (2017). *Effect of credibility and exchange rate pass-through on inflation: An assessment for developing countries*. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 50, 196-244. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2017.03.027>
- viii. Diao, X., & McMillan, M. J. W. D. (2018). *Toward an understanding of economic growth in Africa: A reinterpretation of the Lewis Model*. 109, 511-522.
- ix. Franses, P. H., & Janssens, E. (2018). *Inflation in Africa, 1960–2015*. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 57, 261-292. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intfin.2018.09.005>
- x. Friedman, M. J. T. N. P. D. o. E. (2017). *Quantity theory of money*. 1-31.
- xi. Geda, A., & Seid, E. H. (2015). *The potential for internal trade and regional integration in Africa*. *Journal of African Trade*, 2(1), 19-50. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2015.04.001>

- xii. Gervais, O., Schembri, L., & Suchanek, L. J. J. o. D. E. (2016). *Current account dynamics, real exchange rate adjustment, and the exchange rate regime in emerging-market economies*. 119, 86-99.
- xiii. Ghosh, A. (2014). *How do openness and exchange-rate regimes affect inflation?* *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 34, 190-202. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2014.08.008>
- xiv. Gilpin, R. (2016). *The political economy of international relations*: Princeton University Press.
- xv. Gokal, V., & Hanif, S. (2004). *Relationship between inflation and economic growth*: Economics Department, Reserve Bank of Fiji.
- xvi. Hale, G., & Obstfeld, M. J. J. o. t. E. E. A. (2016). *The Euro and the geography of international debt flows*. 14(1), 115-144.
- xvii. Hartwell, R. M. (2017). *The industrial revolution and economic growth*: Routledge.
- xviii. Kassim, L. (2016). *The revenue implication of trade liberalisation in Sub-Saharan Africa: Some new evidence*. Retrieved from
- xix. Khan, M. S., & Ssnhadji, A. S. J. I. S. p. (2001). *Threshold effects in the relationship between inflation and growth*. 48(1), 1-21.
- xx. Klein, M. W., & Shambaugh, J. C. (2006). *Fixed exchange rates and trade*. *Journal of International Economics*, 70(2), 359-383. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2006.01.001>
- xxi. Krugman, P. (2017). *Crises: The price of globalisation?* In *Economics of Globalisation* (pp. 31-50): Routledge.
- xxii. Lemi, A. (2017). *Aid for trade and Africa's trade performance: Evidence from bilateral trade flows with China and OECD countries*. *Journal of African Trade*, 4(1), 37-60. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2017.12.001>
- xxiii. Levchenko, A. A., & Zhang, J. J. J. o. M. E. (2016). *The evolution of comparative advantage: Measurement and welfare implications*. 78, 96-111.
- xxiv. Lin, J., & Chang, H. J. J. D. p. r. (2009). *Should Industrial Policy in developing countries conform to comparative advantage or defy it? A debate between Justin Lin and Ha-Joon Chang*. 27(5), 483-502.
- xxv. Mbate, M. (2016). *Structural change and industrial policy: A case study of Ethiopia's leather sector*. *Journal of African Trade*, 3(1), 85-100. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2017.01.001>
- xxvi. McCombie, J., & Thirlwall, A. P. (2016). *Economic growth and the balance-of-payments constraint*: Springer.
- xxvii. Meinen, P., & Raff, H. (2018). *International trade and retail market performance and structure: Theory and empirical evidence*. *Journal of International Economics*, 115, 99-114. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2018.08.010>
- xxviii. Menyah, K., Nazlioglu, S., & Wolde-Rufael, Y. (2014). *Financial development, trade openness and economic growth in African countries: New insights from a panel causality approach*. *Economic Modelling*, 37, 386-394. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2013.11.044>
- xxix. Mold, A., & Mukwaya, R. (2016). *Modelling the economic impact of the tripartite free trade area: Its implications for the economic geography of Southern, Eastern and Northern Africa*. *Journal of African Trade*, 3(1), 57-84. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2017.05.003>
- xxx. Morris, M., & Fessehaie, J. (2014). *The industrialisation challenge for Africa: Towards a commodities based industrialisation path*. *Journal of African Trade*, 1(1), 25-36. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2014.10.001>
- xxxi. Ndou, E., & Gumata, N. (2017). *Inflation dynamics in South Africa: The role of thresholds, exchange rate pass-through and inflation expectations on policy trade-offs*: Springer.
- xxxii. Ngo, T. (2017). *Exchange rate exposure of REITs*. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 64, 249-258. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2016.09.002>
- xxxiii. Nguyen, A. D. M., Dridi, J., Unsal, F. D., & Williams, O. H. (2017). *On the drivers of inflation in Sub-Saharan Africa*. *International Economics*, 151, 71-84. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inteco.2017.04.002>

- xxxiv. Njikam, O. (2017). *Export market destination and performance: Firm-level evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa*. *Journal of African Trade*, 4(1), 1-19. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2018.01.001>
- xxxv. Oikawa, K., & Ueda, K. (2018). *The optimal inflation rate under Schumpeterian growth*. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 100, 114-125. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmoneco.2018.07.012>
- xxxvi. Ojo, A. O., & Oluwatayo, I. B. (2016). *Drivers and Challenges of Sustainable Development in Africa*.
- xxxvii. Osakwe, P. N., Santos-Paulino, A. U., & Dogan, B. (2018). *Trade dependence, liberalization, and exports diversification in developing countries*. *Journal of African Trade*, 5(1), 19-34. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2018.09.001>
- xxxviii. Ouyang, A. Y., Rajan, R. S., & Li, J. (2016). *Exchange rate regimes and real exchange rate volatility: Does inflation targeting help or hurt? Japan and the World Economy*, 39, 62-72. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japwor.2016.07.002>
- xxxix. Prebisch, R., Abdoh, D. J. O. R. A.-C. E., Sovereign Rights,, & Decolonization, t. E. C. o. (2017). *One Periphery*. 17, 26.
- xl. Rjoub, H., Aga, M., Oppong, C., Sunju, N., & Fofack, A. J. B.-T. D. S. B. D. (2017). *The Impact of FDI Inflows on Economic Growth: Evidence from Landlocked Countries in Sub-Saharan Africa*. 10(1), 153-168.
- xli. Seck, A. (2016). *Trade facilitation and trade participation: Are sub-Saharan African firms different?* *Journal of African Trade*, 3(1), 23-39. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2017.05.002>
- xlii. Senadza, B., & Diaba, D. D. (2017). *Effect of exchange rate volatility on trade in Sub-Saharan Africa*. *Journal of African Trade*, 4(1), 20-36. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2017.12.002>
- xliii. Steinberg, J. B. (2018). *On the source of U.S. trade deficits: Global saving glut or domestic saving drought? Review of Economic Dynamics*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.red.2018.07.002>
- xliv. Tamgac, U. (2013). *Duration of fixed exchange rate regimes in emerging economies*. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 37, 439-467. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jimonfin.2013.06.015>
- xlv. Were, M. (2015). *Differential effects of trade on economic growth and investment: A cross-country empirical investigation*. *Journal of African Trade*, 2(1), 71-85. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2015.08.002>
- xlvi. Wu, J.-W., & Wu, J.-L. (2018). *Does a flexible exchange rate regime increase inflation persistence?* *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 86, 244-263. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jimonfin.2018.05.002>
- xlvii. Yanamandra, V. (2015). *Exchange rate changes and inflation in India: What is the extent of exchange rate pass-through to imports?* *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 47, 57-68. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eap.2015.07.004>
- xlviii. Zahonogo, P. (2016). *Trade and economic growth in developing countries: Evidence from sub-Saharan Africa*. *Journal of African Trade*, 3(1), 41-56. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joat.2017.02.001>